

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of homo binuclear Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of 1,4-diformylpiperazine derivative

Sulekh Chandra* and Amit Kumar Sharma

Department of Chemistry, Zakir Husain College (University of Delhi), J. L. Nehru Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail : schandra_00@yahoo.com; sharmaamitk@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : The homo binuclear complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} metal ions with a binucleating tetradentate Schiff's base ligand 1,4-diformylpiperazinebis(carbohydrazone) have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, IR, UV, EPR spectral studies and thermal studies. The general stoichiometries of the complexes are found to be [Cr₂(H₂L)X₄], [Ni₂(H₂L)X₂] and [M₂(H₂L)X₂(H₂O)₄], where M = Mn^{II} and Co^{II}, H₂L = dideprotonated ligand, and X = NO₃⁻ and OAc⁻. The studies reveal that the complexes possess the binuclear monomeric compositions and octahedral geometry for Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes, whereas the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have tetragonal and square planar geometries, respectively.

Keywords : Tetradentate Schiff's base ligand, bimetallic complexes, spectral studies, TGA.

Introduction

The synthesis of polydentate Schiff's base ligands has attracted a great deal of attention to form both cyclic and acyclic coordination compounds^{1,2}. Moreover, the ligands with amide or thioamide bonds are capable to show versatile chelating behavior and form variety of coordination compounds³. However, the binuclear complexes have been studied due to their relevance in various branches of science viz. natural science, chemistry and biology. For several decades much efforts have been devoted to the studies of bimetallic complexes with polydentate chelating agents⁴⁻⁶.

In this paper, we report the synthesis, spectral and thermogravimetric analysis studies of homo binuclear chromium(III), manganese(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes with a binucleating tetradentate Schiff's base ligand, 1,4-diformylpiperazine bis(carbohydrazone).

Experimental

Materials :

1,4-Diformylpiperazine and carbohydrazide were procured from Sigma-Aldrich and used as supplied. All other chemicals and solvents were commercially available (E. Merck, Fluka and Sisco International). Solvents were used as received.

Physical measurements :

The microanalyses were performed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 analyzer. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in the region 4000–200 cm⁻¹ on a FT-IR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer using DMSO/DMF as a solvent. X-band EPR spectra were recorded for solids and solutions on an E4-EPR spectrometer at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature. The molar conductance of complexes was measured in DMSO/DMF at room temperature on an ELICO (CM 82T) conductivity bridge. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄.5H₂O as calibrant. Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) were recorded in a static nitrogen atmosphere with heating rate of 5 °C/min, using Diamond TG/DTA Thermogravimetric/Differential Thermal Analyzer.

Synthesis of Schiff's base ligand :

The Schiff's base ligand 1,4-diformylpiperazine bis(carbohydrazone) was synthesized by the method as reported earlier⁷ (Scheme 1).

Synthesis of complexes :

The complexes were synthesised by refluxing an ethanolic solution (30 mL) of ligand (1 mmol) with an

Scheme 1. Synthesis of ligand.

aqueous ethanolic solution (50 mL) of corresponding metal salt like nitrate or acetate (2 mmol) for 10–20 h at 70–85 °C. On cooling overnight at 0 °C the colored complex was precipitated out, which was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried under vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Results and discussion

The microanalytical data and physical characterization of complexes are presented in Table 1. As we reported earlier⁷ that the Schiff's base ligand exhibits keto-

enol tautomerism due to presence of amide bonds and coordinate to metal atoms in dideprotonated form, the ligand forms bimetallic homonuclear complexes. The analytical data correspond to the general formulae [Cr₂(H₂L)X₄], [Ni₂(H₂L)X₂] and [M₂(H₂L)X₂(H₂O)₄] of the complexes, where M = Mn^{II} and Co^{II}, H₂L = dideprotonated ligand, and X = NO₃⁻ and OAc⁻. The molar conductance of the complexes in DMSO/DMF indicates that the complexes are non-electrolytes⁸ with the compositions viz. [Cr₂(H₂L)X₄], [Ni₂(H₂L)X₂] and [M₂(H₂L)X₂(H₂O)₄].

Table 1. Microanalytical data of complexes with their physical properties

Sl. no.	Complex	Color	M.p. (°C)	Molar conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Yield (%)	Microanalytical data (%) : Calcd. (Found)			
						M	C	H	N
1.	[Cr ₂ (H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₄] Cr ₂ C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₁₀ O ₁₄	Violet	290	11	65	16.35 (16.31)	15.09 (15.05)	2.52 (2.47)	30.82 (30.78)
2.	[Cr ₂ (H ₂ L)(OAc) ₄] Cr ₂ C ₁₆ H ₂₈ N ₁₀ O ₁₀	Violet	> 300	17	67	16.67 (16.70)	30.77 (30.72)	4.49 (4.45)	22.44 (22.38)
3.	[Mn ₂ (H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] Mn ₂ C ₈ H ₂₄ N ₁₂ O ₁₂	White	> 300	17	55	18.63 (18.56)	16.28 (16.21)	4.07 (4.01)	28.48 (28.42)
4.	[Mn ₂ (H ₂ L)(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] Mn ₂ C ₁₂ H ₃₀ N ₁₀ O ₁₀	White	> 300	8	64	18.82 (18.85)	24.66 (24.71)	5.14 (5.09)	23.98 (23.91)
5.	[Co ₂ (H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] Co ₂ C ₈ H ₂₄ N ₁₂ O ₁₂	Pink	> 300	21	60	19.71 (19.66)	16.06 (16.11)	4.01 (3.95)	28.10 (28.03)
6.	[Co ₂ (H ₂ L)(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] Co ₂ C ₁₂ H ₃₀ N ₁₀ O ₁₀	Pink	292	14	66	19.91 (19.83)	24.33 (24.26)	5.07 (5.01)	23.65 (23.58)
7.	[Ni ₂ (H ₂ L)(NO ₃) ₂] Ni ₂ C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₁₂ O ₈	Greyish blue	> 300	27	63	22.35 (22.26)	18.27 (18.19)	3.05 (2.99)	31.98 (31.92)
8.	[Ni ₂ (H ₂ L)(OAc) ₂] Ni ₂ C ₁₂ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₆	Greyish blue	> 300	29	65	22.60 (22.52)	27.72 (27.67)	4.24 (4.18)	26.95 (26.89)

The low value of magnetic moments, i.e. 3.14–3.18, 5.16–5.20 and 3.25–3.32 for Cr^{III}, Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes, respectively indicates the antiferromagnetic interaction between the metal atoms. The complexes of Ni^{II} are found to be diamagnetic.

IR spectra :

The comparative IR data of free ligand and its complexes are summarized in Table 2. A shift of amide I (1675 cm⁻¹), amide II (1624 cm⁻¹) and amide III (1551 cm⁻¹) IR

Table 2. Comparative IR data of compounds

Compd. Ligand	Amide I	Amide II	Amide III	$\nu(M-N)$	$\nu(M-O)$
	1675	1624	1551	-	-
1	1619	1588	1503	423	517
2	1624	1560	1450	543	613
3	1654	1598	1492	439	504
4	1636	1549	1508	391	572
5	1637	1602	1514	379	511
6	1629	1577	1528	401	527
7	1658	1598	1533	477	510
8	1636	1570	1530	404	502

bands of free ligand to the lower value in its complexes is consistent with the coordination of enolic oxygens and azomethine nitrogens to the central metal ion^{7,9}. Moreover, in the IR spectra of complexes, the new bands appear in the range 391–543 and 502–613 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(M-O)$ stretching vibrations¹⁰. This indicates that the ligand acts as tetradentate coordinating species bonded to metal atom through ONNO donor sites.

The nitrate complexes show IR bands at 1438–1494 (ν_5), 1268–1320 (ν_1) and 1028–1088 (ν_2) cm⁻¹ and value

of $\Delta(\nu_5 - \nu_1)$ i.e. 170–193 cm⁻¹ indicates the bidentate coordination of NO₃⁻ ion¹¹. The acetato complexes show the IR bands in the region 1399–1490 and 1316–1381 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{as}(OAc)$ and $\nu_s(OAc)$ stretching vibrations. The $\Delta\nu$ i.e. 59–110 cm⁻¹ suggests the bidentate coordination of the OAc anion¹². In the IR spectra of complexes 3, 4, 5 and 6, the bands in the region 741–868 and 583–648 cm⁻¹ are also present which are characteristic bands of pr(H₂O) and pw(H₂O). These bands are assigned to the coordinated water molecule¹².

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of complexes were recorded in DMSO/DMF solutions and the data are presented in Table 3.

The electronic spectra of Cr^{III} complexes display the transitions in the range 15873–15945 and 22471–26238 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) spin allowed *d-d* transitions. These transitions reveal that Cr^{III} ion is in octahedral environment¹³. The electronic spectra of the complexes also display the third transition in the range 35714–36788 cm⁻¹ due to charge transfer band.

The electronic spectra of Mn^{II} complexes display the absorption bands in the range 18587–18621, 22471–24298, 27397–28169 and 36496 cm⁻¹. These transitions may be assigned to the ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4D)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. The band at 45454 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the charge transfer band. These transitions suggest the octahedral geometry for the complexes¹³.

Table 3. Magnetic, electronic spectral data and ligand field parameters of complexes

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)	C (cm ⁻¹)	β	LFSE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	F_4	F_2
1	3.14	15945, 26238, 36788	1594.5	650	-	0.63	228.60	-	-
2	3.18	15873, 22471, 35714	1587.3	647	-	0.63	227.57	-	-
3	5.16	18621, 22471, 27397, 45454	1862.1	703	3086	0.73	-	88.2	1143.9
4	5.20	18587, 24298, 28169, 36496	1858.7	553	3753	0.58	-	107.2	1089.1
5	3.25	10706, 18680, 22125, 27322, 28910	1229.16	819.44	-	0.73	117.48	-	-
6	3.32	10427, 18621, 22321, 27322, 38022	1225.46	875.33	-	0.78	117.29	-	-
7	Dia.	13123, 18587, 27247, 38910	1312.3	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	Dia.	15479, 18867, 24154, 38759	1547.9	-	-	-	-	-	-

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes display the absorption bands in the region 10427–10706, 18621–18680 and 22125–22321 cm⁻¹. These transitions may be assigned to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) \nu_1$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F) \nu_2$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) \nu_3$ transitions, respectively. These transitions correspond to the tetragonal geometry around the Co^{II} metal centre¹³. The absorption bands in the electronic spectra of the complexes are also present in the region 27322–38022 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to the intra-ligand and charge transfer bands.

The absorption spectra of Ni^{II} complexes display *d-d* transition bands in the range 13123–15479, 18587–18867 and 24154–27247 cm⁻¹. The lowest energy transition corresponds to the transition ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}(d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}) \nu_1$ which suggests that the energy levels order is $d_{z^2} < d_{xy}$ ¹⁴. The other transitions corresponds to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}(d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}) \nu_2$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g(d_{xy}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}) \nu_3$, respectively. These transitions reveal that the nickel complexes possess square planar geometry and *D*_{4h} symmetry¹⁵. The complexes display ν_1 band at higher energy in comparison to that of the octahedral complexes. This is because of the reason that the crystal field energy for square planar complexes is large and the energy separation between $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital and the next lowest orbital is higher as compared to the octahedral complexes¹⁵.

The ligand field parameters like *B*, *C* (Racah parameters), 10 *Dq*, covalency factor β and LFSE have been calculated and are summarized in Table 3. The condon shortly parameters *F*₂ and *F*₄ for Mn^{II} complexes have been evaluated as a function of Racah parameters *B* and *C*.

EPR spectra :

The EPR spectral data of the complexes are presented in Table 4. The X-band EPR spectra of Cr^{III} complexes

at room temperature show a broad signal at $g_{iso} = 1.9703$ – 2.3012 in solid state (Fig 1a). Because the signal does not show any hyperfine splitting, the parameters *D* and *E* can not be estimated. The EPR results of complexes are consistent with the presence of hexacoordinated Cr^{III} centers^{16–18}.

The X-band EPR spectra of Mn^{II} complexes in polycrystalline form at room temperature as well as liquid nitrogen temperature give only one signal at $g_{iso} = 2.0057$ – 2.1746 (Fig. 1b)¹⁹, whereas the EPR spectra of complexes in solution give the sextet at $g_{iso} = 2.0003$ – 2.1046 due to electron spin nuclear spin coupling (⁵⁵Mn, *I* = 5/2). The electron spin-nuclear spin hyperfine coupling constant *A*_{iso} values (88.5–96.5) are consistent with an octahedral environment around Mn^{II} ion^{20,21}.

The X-band EPR spectra of Co^{II} complexes at liquid nitrogen temperature display the broad signal with the *g* value in the range : $g_{\parallel} = 2.5008$ – 2.6218 , $g_{\perp} = 1.8901$ – 1.9237 and $g_{iso} = 2.0937$ – 2.1564 , corresponding to the tetragonal symmetry around Co^{II} atoms^{22,23}. The EPR spectra of Co^{II} complexes give the signals only at low temperature. This is due to the fact that the high-spin Co^{II} ions have the fast spin-relaxation time.

Thermogravimetric analysis :

The thermogravimetric studies of the complexes were carried out in the temperature range 30–600 °C with a sample heating rate 5 °C/min in a static nitrogen atmosphere. TGA study of the complexes indicates that the complexes 3–6 undergo first step decomposition with weight loss exp. 11.95–12.29% (*ca.* 12.04–12.37%) between 190–220 °C due to loss of the four coordinated

Table 4. EPR spectral data of complexes

Complex	Polycrystalline form				Solution form			
	<i>g</i> _⊥ (LNT)	<i>g</i> _∥ (LNT)	<i>g</i> _{iso} (RT)	<i>g</i> _{iso} (LNT)	<i>g</i> _{iso} (RT)	<i>A</i> _{iso} (RT)	<i>g</i> _{iso} (LNT)	<i>A</i> _{iso} (LNT)
1	-	-	2.3012	-	-	-	-	-
2	-	-	1.9703	-	-	-	-	-
3	-	-	2.0057	2.0098	2.0108	88.5	2.1046	96.5
4	-	-	2.0192	2.1736	2.0003	92.5	2.0879	96.0
5	1.8901	2.5008	2.0937	-	-	-	-	-
6	1.9237	4.6218	2.1564	-	-	-	-	-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. EPR spectra of complexes at RT in polycrystalline form : (a) $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{OAc})_4]$ and (b) $[\text{Mn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{OAc})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$.

water molecules whereas the complexes 1, 2, 7 and 8 do not undergo any decomposition in this region. This suggests the absence of any coordinated and lattice water molecule in these complexes. The complexes show the decomposition exp. 34.89–47.39% (ca. 34.94–47.48%) between 330–410 °C due to removal of coordinated anions

and half part of the ligand. Finally the complexes undergo decomposition exp. 26.55–31.87% (ca. 27.66–31.96%) between 430–550 °C due to loss of remaining part of ligand. The final residue was analyzed by IR spectra and identified as metal oxide. The structures of the complexes are given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Structures of complexes : (a) $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_4]$, (b) $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{OAc})_4]$, (c) $[\text{M}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, (d) $[\text{M}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{OAc})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$, (e) $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ and (f) $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{OAc})_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ and Co^{II} .

Conclusions :

The IR, electronic, EPR spectral and thermal studies led to the conclusion that the Cr^{III}, Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes under study are six coordinated with octahedral environment for Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes, whereas the Co^{II} complexes possess tetragonal geometry. The Ni^{II} complexes are four coordinated with square planar coordination environment. The analytical data, low value magnetic moments, high thermal stability and insolubility in common organic solvents support the bimetallic composition of the complexes. The value of covalency factor (β) less than unity indicates the covalent nature of the complexes.

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